

Students' Attitudes and Motivation towards English Language Learning in Borgou Secondary Schools in Benin

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Résumé

Cette étude examine les attitudes et la motivation des apprenants envers l'apprentissage de la langue anglaise dans les collèges du Borgou au Bénin. Elle étudie comment les perceptions des élèves, les buts, et les environnements d'apprentissage influencent leur engagement pour l'acquisition de l'Anglais. La méthode utilisée est quantitative et qualitative. Les données ont été recueillies à travers des questionnaires et interviews administrés aux apprenants des écoles sélectionnées, complétées par les observations pédagogiques. Les résultats révèlent une interaction complexe entre les attitudes positives et négatives. Pendant que certains apprenants considèrent l'Anglais comme une opportunité de réussite scolaire, des opportunités d'emploi, et une communication globale, d'autres trouvent ça difficile, comme une langue étrangère, et de moindre importance dans leur contexte socio-culturel proche. La motivation est influencée par des facteurs intégratifs, tels que le désir de se connecter avec des communautés plus larges, et des facteurs instrumentaux, surtout des opportunités de carrière. Cependant, l'exposition limitée à l'anglais en dehors de la classe et le manque de ressources fragilisent la motivation à long terme. L'étude met en évidence la nécessité de politiques d'accompagnement, de formation enseignante et de participation des parents pour encourager des attitudes et une motivation plus solides.

Mots-Clés: *Attitudes, Motivation, Apprenants, Anglais, Enseignant.*

Abstract

This study examines learners' attitudes and motivation toward learning English in middle schools in Borgou, Benin. It explores how students' perceptions, goals, and learning environments influence their commitment to acquiring English. The method used is quantitative and qualitative. Data were collected through questionnaires and interviews administered to learners in selected schools, supplemented by pedagogical observations. The results reveal a complex interaction between positive and negative attitudes. While some learners see English as an opportunity for academic success, employment opportunities, and global communication, others find it difficult as a foreign language and of lesser importance in their immediate socio-cultural context.

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Motivation is influenced by integrative factors, such as the desire to connect with wider communities, and instrumental factors, especially career opportunities. However, limited exposure to English outside the classroom and a lack of resources undermine long-term motivation. The study highlights the need for support policies, teacher training, and parental involvement to encourage stronger attitudes and motivation.

Keywords: *Attitudes, Motivation, Learners, English. Teacher.*

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Introduction

Nowadays, learning English has become more essential in all domains. It is taught from lower level to higher level. It becomes a compulsory subject at secondary subject in national examination. Even, most of people are interested in learning it (Jefiza, 2017).

In learning English, students have some reasons. Every student has different reasons. For example, students want to learn English because they are interested in English - speaking music, movies and culture. They want to understand films, series, of social media trends. Some of them learn English because a large portion of the internet's content is in English. Then, students in Benin live around people from Nigeria which is an English country, so they will learn English to be able to communicate well. “The use of computer - based entertainment such as English language movies, music, and online videos can significantly enhance learner's motivation and exposure to authentic language input” Silviyanti (2014, p.42).

Apart from the significance of motivation, some motivation problems can be noticed in learning English. In school, the researcher has revealed that some students showed a lack of motivation in learning English (Jefiza, 2017). They found English is difficult and they did not like English class, so they exhibited poor attitudes in learning English (Jefiza, 2017). Furthermore, some students were not satisfied with their English because after many years of leaning English they still could not speak English properly. Even, some final year secondary school students said they have learned English since they were in year 7. Nevertheless, it was still difficult for them to communicate in English properly.

Success in learning is closely related to motivation. Motivation can be defined as the internal or external drive, desire, or willingness that influences a learner's engagement, effort, and persistence in achieving academic goals. According to Cook & Artino (2016, p.5) “Motivation is the process that initiates, guides, and sustains goal - directed behavior, and in education, it plays a central time in the quality and quantity of learning”.

In addition Ryan & Deci (2020, p.2) distinguished between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. They stated that “intrinsic motivation refers to doing something because

it is inherently interesting or enjoyable, while extrinsic motivation involves doing something because it leads to a separable outcome such as rewards or avoidance of punishment".

Additionally, Reeve, (2018, p.134) claimed that "intrinsic motivation emerges from interest, curiosity, or inherent satisfaction in an activity, whereas extrinsic motivation is regulated by external demands, incentives, or social pressures". Thus, as a teacher, we need to know learners' motivation in learning and help them build motivation intrinsically and extrinsically (Jefiza, 2017).

What is more, motivation can affect someone responses and acts, that is called attitudes. Attitudes are learned tendencies or predispositions to respond a person, object, idea or situation. In education, students' attitudes toward a subject (like English) can influence their motivation, engagement, and academic success.

These two perspectives are complementary: the first explains what attitudes are, while the second demonstrates how attitudes influence behavior. Together, they provide a solid theoretical foundation for analyzing students' attitudes toward English language learning, especially in contexts like Benin, where affective and motivational factors play an important role in second language acquisition.

Up to now, there are many studies that have been conducted in the field of attitudes and motivation in learning English.

Another study conducted by Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (2021, p.3) Investigates students' motivation in second language acquisition. It emphasizes the role of learners' attitudes, cultural context, and motivation types (integrative, instrumental, intrinsic, and extrinsic).

The facts above prove that every student has different motivation and attitudes in learning English. The motivation and attitudes will lead students to success or failure. It's is compulsory for teacher to explore attitudes and motivation of students first before determining teaching strategies in the classroom. Based on that, the research questions have been elaborated (Jefiza, 2017).

Research Questions

What are students' attitudes towards learning English language?

What types of motivation drive Borgou secondary school students to learn English, and how do contextual factors such as teaching practices, resources, and sociolinguistic environment impact these motivations?

Research Hypotheses

Students with positive attitudes toward English are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of classroom participation, persistence, and achievement than those with negative attitudes.

Instrumental motivations (e.g., passing exams, future careers, scholarships) will be stronger predictor of students' engagement with English language learning in Borgou secondary schools than integrative motivations (e.g., connecting with English - speaking cultures), due to limited exposure to English outside the classroom.

Significance of the Study

The research is expected to make beneficial contribution to the field of English learning, especially for teachers in focusing on attitudes and motivation of students.

This study is significant for its potential to improve English language education in Borgou secondary schools, inform policy and practice, and contribute to the body of knowledge on language learning motivation and attitudes.

Literature Review

In Borgou, a multilingual environment with French- medium instructions and local mother tongues (e.g., Bariba, Fon, Dendi, Nago, Fulfude), English remains largely confined to classrooms. Learners' attitudes are shaped by the prestige of English and its perceived distance from local identities. Their motivation is primarily instrumental (exams, grants, mobility). Learning experiences are hampered by large class sizes, limited resources, and fluctuating teacher proficiency, undermining autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2020, p.95).

Ryan and Deci (2020, p.100) argue that autonomy - supportive teaching (e.g., offering choice, scaffolding, rationale, feedback) enhances autonomous motivation and self-efficacy). What is more, Deci and Ryan (2000, p.82) affirm that parental values, peer norms and labor-market signals strongly influence utility perceptions and the ought - to - self. To enhance motivation quality, schools should promote internalization helping students align English learning with personally meaningful future.

Gardner and Lambert (1972, pp.3-4) distinguish between instrumental motivation (driven by practical goals like jobs or exams), and integrative motivation, where learners aspire to connect with the culture of the target language.

According to Baker (1992, p.10) Attitudes toward English significantly affect learners' engagement. Positive Attitudes often correlate with perseverance and active participation. In contexts where English is linked to socio economic advancement, students may develop both high instrumental motivation and strong attitudes, even in the face of limited resources.

Williams and Burden (1997, p.36) demonstrate that teachers play a vital role in shaping attitudes and sustaining motivation. The classroom environment, peer interactions, and teaching methodologies can foster or hinder enthusiasm for learning English.

Methodology

This study employs quantitative and qualitative methods. The data were gathered using questionnaire and interview. In this study, the participants were selected from three secondary schools in Borgou. The number of participants involved in this study was 24 participants who were selected through purposive sampling to reflect different academic levels and language proficiencies. Purposive sampling (also called judgemental or selective sampling) is a non - probability sampling technique where the researcher deliberately selects participants based on specific characteristics of qualities that are relevant to the study. It is commonly used in qualitative research when the goal is to gain deep insights from a specific group of people who can provide rich and relevant information. "Purposive sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research to identify and select information - rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources" Palinkas et al (2015, p.533). There are no difficulties in conducting the study because the researcher also worked as English teacher. Then, the students and teacher in that class were really helpful in giving their participation.

The data in this study were collected in May 5th , 2025 by using questionnaire and interview.

Questionnaire

In this study, a questionnaire is used to give information in written response. A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions or other prompts for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. It is widely used in survey research to collect quantitative and qualitative data on opinions, behaviors, experiences, or characteristics. According to Bryman (2016, p.227) “A questionnaire is a structured set of written questions designed to collect standardized information from a large number of people in a consistent way”. The questionnaire consisted of 16 close ended questions that are divided into four parts: positive attitudes, negative attitudes, intrinsic motivation, and extrinsic motivation. Each part consists of four questions that are written in English and also translated into French to ensure complete understanding. This questionnaire used Likert scales as instrument. ” The Likert scales is a popular tool in survey research, used to capture the intensity of respondents' feelings or attitudes towards a particular statement ” (Joshi, A., Kale, S., & Pal, D. K., 2015, p.396). It typically asks respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements, using a fixed range of responses.

Interview

An interview is a qualitative data collection method that involves a structured or unstructured conversation between a researcher and a respondent, with the aim of gathering in-depth information about the respondent's experiences, opinions, attitudes, or behavior. According to Alshenqeti (2014, p.39): “An interview is a verbal interaction between two people, where the interviewer asks questions to obtain information from the interviewee”. For this reason, the interview was done to get participants' responses in-depth and to examine attitudes, interests and feelings.

The interview was done after students had filled the questionnaire. All the participants were interviewed. This interview was conducted to gain oral response from the participants. Interview in this study is useful for exploring participants' attitudes, feelings, and motivations.

Data Analysis

The data collected in this study are quantitative and qualitative ones. The quantitative data of the questionnaire were analyzed in terms of means and percentages. As far as the qualitative data are concerned, a content analysis was used. In the analysis process, the interviewees' responses for each question were transcribed before the responses were analyzed in terms of themes related to the study objectives (Jefiza, 2017).

Findings and Discussion

Data from Questionnaire

The questionnaires were distributed to know student's motivation and attitudes towards English language learning.

Figure 1. Data

N°	Statements	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1	English is an important subject			30%	70%

2	I'll learn English as much as possible		10%		90%
3	Learning English is interesting			40%	60%
4	I always do my exercises in English		20%	20%	60%
5	It is difficult to learn English		20%	60%	20%
6	I prefer to read books in french during English classes	30%		20%	50%
7	I make an effort to follow the teacher during English classes	25%		50%	25%
8	Learning English is a waste of time	25%	25%	50%	
9	I learn English to improve my English language competencies			60%	40%
10	Learning English can help me understand other cultures			40%	60%
11	I learn English because it is useful and successful			20%	80%
12	I learn English because I want to communicate with people living in English speaking countries.			30%	70%
13	Learning English is useful for getting a job			25%	75%
14	I study English because I want to do well at school		20%	20%	60%
15	I study English to please my parents			50%	50%
16	I study English to speak fluently like native speakers.		25%	50%	25%

The questionnaire number 1-4 investigates learners' positive attitudes in learning English. Statement number 1 is about the importance of English. 70% of students strongly agreed that English is an important subject whereas 30% of them agree. Then, according to all the participants, they strongly agreed to learn English as much as possible. As far as "Learning English is interesting is concerned, 90% of students strongly agreed with that whereas 10% of the students disagreed. 60% of students strongly agreed that they "always do their exercises in English", whereas 20% agreed and 20% disagreed with that. From this part, most of the students show positive attitudes to learn English and this will lead them to proficiency.

The questionnaire number 5-8 shows students' negative attitudes in learning English. 60% of students agreed that it's difficult to learn English, whereas 20% strongly agreed and 20% disagreed with that statement. 50% of students strongly agreed with the statement "I prefer to read books in French rather than English", whereas 30% of them strongly disagreed and 20% agreed. As far as "I make an effort to follow the teacher during English class, 50% of students agreed; 25% strongly agreed and 25% strongly disagreed. 80% of the students disagreed with the statement "Learning English is a waste of time", whereas 20% strongly agreed and the rest strongly disagreed.

In addition, students' positive attitudes and intrinsic motivation in learning English are found in number 9-12. 60% of students agreed that they learn English to improve their English language competencies, and 40% strongly agreed. 60% students strongly agreed that learning English can help them understand other cultures, and 40% agreed. Most of the students strongly agreed that learning English is useful and successful. 70% of the students strongly agreed that they learn English because they want to

communicate with people living in English speaking countries, whereas 30% disagreed. Thus, most of the students had good intrinsic motivation in learning English.

Finally, students' extrinsic motivation is found in statement number 13 until 16. 75% of students strongly agreed that learning English is useful for getting a job ; and 25% agreed . 60% of students strongly agreed that they study English to please their parents Whereas 50% agreed. 50% agreed that they study English to speak fluently like English native speakers, whereas 25% agreed and the rest disagreed.

Based on the data above, most of students have positive attitudes in English language learning, but some of them have negative attitudes. In learning English, most of the students are guided by extrinsic motivation rather than intrinsic motivation.

Data from Interview

Some questions in interview were taken from questionnaire. The interview was used to clarify the responses from questionnaire. After being checked, the results of interview from 24 participants showed supported result of the questionnaire. The data is concluded here.

Students' motivation in learning English.

There are two kinds of motivation: intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. Most of the students said they learnt English to please their parents, that proved that they were extrinsically motivated. They also said that learning English is useful and successful for them.

Students' attitudes in learning English.

Most of the students plan to learn English as much as possible. They always do their exercises in English and they found that learning English is interesting. Nevertheless, if they had to choose, they preferred to read books in French rather than English.

The findings show that most students in Borgou have positive attitudes towards English language learning. They consider English as a key to academic success, better job opportunities, and global communication. Nevertheless, the positive attitudes are often instrumental rather than integrative. In Borgou, instrumental motivation dominates, especially in public schools where English is viewed as a subject necessary to pass national exams. Some students also expressed negative attitudes. Most learners are extrinsically motivated for they learn English to pass exams (eg. BEPC, BAC) and a smaller number of learner's showed intrinsic motivation.

Implications

Literature affirms that students' attitudes and motivation are dynamic and responsive to pedagogy and context. EFL learners benefit from vivid, attainable future - self imagery and need supportive instruction (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021, p.72). For Borgou, promising approaches include professional development for autonomy - supportive instruction, project - based tasks, communicative assessment, and low exposure opportunities. Some motivated students perform better when engaging with pedagogical practices, but lack of interactive exposure, and insufficient teaching strategies heavily impact attitude and motivation. Teachers don't implement pronunciation skills, communicative tasks, and resulting students' incapacity to speak English fluently.

Conclusion

This study has examined students' attitudes and motivation toward English language learning in Borgou secondary schools, highlighting the complex interplay between learners' perceptions aspirations, and the contextual realities of their educational environment. Findings suggest that while students generally recognize the importance of English as a tool for academic advancement, career opportunities, and global communication, their motivation is shaped predominantly by instrumental factors such as passing examinations and securing future employment. Integrative orientations, through present, remain limited due to restricted exposure to English - speaking cultures and scarce opportunities for authentic language use outside the classroom.

In Borgou, some motivated students perform better when engaging with pedagogical practices, but lack of interactive exposure, and insufficient teaching strategies heavily impact attitude and motivation. Enhancing students' motivation and attitudes requires a holistic approach that addresses classroom practices, school resources, ensuring that English learning in Borgou becomes not only an academic requirement but also a meaningful personal and social endeavor.

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